

LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE STRENGTH OF A DUCTILE HYBRID FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER BAR FOR EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: Reinforced concrete (R/C) structures, especially pavements and bridge decks that constitute vital elements of the infrastructure of all industrialized societies, are deteriorating prematurely. Structural repair and upgrading of these structural elements have become a more economical option for constructed facilities especially in the United States and Canada. In regions of moderate to high seismicity, R/C structures are designed based on their ability to absorb seismic energy. This absorption capacity exists due to the ability of the reinforcement to yield, thereby producing large inelastic strains.

The low-cycle fatigue behavior of the DHFRP bar was investigated at Drexel University by placing the bars in beam and beam-column concrete elements. Unlike most current FRP bars, the DHFRP bar has a behavior that simulates the stress-strain characteristics of conventional steel reinforcement. The DHFRP bar exhibits a bilinear stress-strain behavior, which shows significant material toughness for all bar sizes. These bars are produced using a combination of both traditional pultrusion and braiding processes simultaneously, creating a Braidtrusion process, and have been produced in 3-mm and 5-mm diameter model sizes and a 10-mm diameter prototype size. The bars are a material hybrid of aramid (Kevlar 49) fibers and carbon (Thornel P-55S). The design methodology and manufacturing process is described in Hampton et al. (1) and Lam et al. (2).

The uniaxial tensile strength was first investigated and shows significant ductility. High initial stiffness and large elongation after yield was illustrated. The DHFRP bars were then placed in prototype reinforced concrete (R/C) beams and beam-columns. The beams were loaded in three-point bending under unidirectional static load while the beam-columns were subjected to both a transverse load applied at the beam end and axial compression. The lateral load was applied in increasing cycles and fully reversed until failure. Both tests demonstrated significant ductility and material toughness of the DHFRP bars, especially under reverse cyclic loading. The energy absorption capacity of the material was demonstrated through the hysteretic load-deflection and moment-rotation behavior of the beam-columns, and through definitions of ductility indices based on displacement, rotation, and curvature. Also, the interaction between axial load and bending moment was investigated. The ability of DHFRP to yield with significant inelastic strains is an indication of the energy absorption capability of the reinforcement under reverse cyclic loading, a crucial concern for reinforced concrete structures, especially those subjected to earthquake loading.

KEYWORDS: Reinforcements, Structures, Textiles, Fatigue Resistance, Reinforced Concrete.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced concrete (R/C) structures especially pavements and bridge decks that constitute vital elements of the infrastructure of all industrialized societies are deteriorating prematurely (5). This paper describes the energy absorption capabilities of a second generation ductile hybrid FRP reinforcement developed in the form of a ductile hybrid bar (DHFRP) which simulates the stress-strain characteristics of conventional steel reinforcement (3,4). The developed FRP bar possesses a ductile behavior, which is intrinsic to its hybrid fiber composition and the hybrid geometric architecture of its fibers (1). A combined experimental and analytical approach is taken to develop the architecture of the desired ductile hybrid FRP reinforcement using advanced 2-D and 3-D braiding techniques pioneered in the Fibrous Materials Research Center of Drexel University (2).

Using a combination of high modulus carbon (Thornel P-55S) and aramid (Kevlar 49) fibers, 10-mm diameter bars with a tri-linear stress-strain tensile curve with a definite yield, an ultimate strength higher than yield and an ultimate failure at between 2 % and 3.5 % strain were obtained. Excellent bond characteristics were obtained by integrating ribs into the braided jacket to increase the mechanical interaction at the bar to concrete interface. Results have been presented from concrete beam-columns 38.1 mm x 38.1 mm in section and 254 mm long reinforced with ductile hybrid FRP bars which produced ductility indices that were essentially the same to those of a companion steel reinforced beam-column. The ductility indices were based on definitions of ductility according to displacement, rotation, and energy considerations. The tensile strength and flexural interaction in concrete beams have been described by (1).

An in-line braiding and pultrusion process was developed to produce high quality DHFRP bars up to 10-mm nominal diameter (2). Using the results from the tensile tests and fracture analysis, the stress-strain behavior of the DHFRP bars was fully characterized.

DESIGN CONCEPT OF THE DUCTILE HYBRID FRP (DHFRP)

Ductility is the ability of a material or structural member to undergo large inelastic deformations without distress. In the extreme event of a structure loaded to failure, it should be able to undergo large deflections at or near its maximum load carrying capacity. This will give forewarning of failure and prevent total collapse and may save lives. In statically indeterminate concrete structures, ductility of the members at the critical sections is necessary to allow moment redistribution to take place. In order to achieve ductility in reinforced concrete structures without using conventional steel rebar, a new design methodology was introduced by the authors to identify suitable fibrous composite materials that mimic the stress-strain characteristics of steel. Taking advantage of the design flexibility and the wide availability of manufacturing capacity in the industry, braided structures were employed as the primary fiber architecture for the construction of the reported ductile hybrid FRP rebar system.

The design methodology of the DHFRP bars follows a structural hierarchy of fibrous assemblies (6). This hierarchy includes various geometric levels to be studied including material properties, fiber and yarn packing and braid helix angle. By using hierarchical design, there are at least five tailorable levels of design that can be utilized in order to obtain an optimized composite. This design methodology is fundamental in the design of the DHFRP bars. .

MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF DHFRP

Processing parameters for producing samples of the hybrid FRP include the braiding profile and the processing speed. A prototype-manufacturing machine was designed incorporating these processing

parameters. The process, a combination of braiding and pultrusion, is called braidtrusion. The process includes a 24-carrier braider, a resin applicator, a heated die for proper cure and a heated chamber for continued post-cure. Four carriers are used for rib yarns and the other 20 are used for braiding yarns. These form a braided sleeve of Kevlar fibers. The core fibers are placed on a creel and form a unidirectional elastic core of carbon fibers. Details of the process are explained in (2).

EXPERIMENTAL TESTING PROGRAM

Figure 1 shows the load-strain curves and the design load-strain curve for all of the tests of 10-mm diameter prototype bars. The procedure for tensile testing was explained in (1). Work on tensile testing of other FRP was presented in (7). Load is presented instead of stress since there are various ways to present stress (3). For design purposes of R/C structures, only the strain and the load are necessary for proper design. These curves demonstrate a tri-linear load-strain behavior with a definite yield point, an elasto-plastic region, and a strain hardening region. This failure mechanism is unique to DHFRP and is a result of the design of the material.

Figure 1 Design Load-Strain Behavior for Prototype DHFRP Bars

LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF DHFRP IN CONCRETE COLUMNS: It is crucial for a structure to be able to absorb energy, especially during an earthquake event. Therefore, a ductile reinforcing material is needed for reinforced concrete structures. Steel provides this ductility for R/C elements, but many FRP's are linear elastic to failure and do not possess significant energy absorption capacity under reverse cyclic loading. Contrary to this, however, the DHFRP developed shows significant energy absorption capacity. Work on concrete beam-columns subjected to simulated earthquake loading was done by (10) and (11).

Post-elastic behavior of reinforced concrete members is critical in the proper design for seismic response of R/C structures. The reverse cyclic loading (i.e., reversed cycles of tension and compression) is a

method to simulate the loading due to earthquakes. The column performance was based on three criteria: column moment capacity, displacement ductility, and overall hysteresis behavior. The degradation and energy dissipation characteristics were also investigated. These criteria were obtained from the lateral load-deflection plots (applied lateral load versus tip displacement). The hysteresis curves provide several important quantifications including stiffness (slope), peak values of lateral load and deflection, and the shape of the hysteresis loops. The area under the hysteresis loops gives the total energy dissipated by the column under cyclic loading. This is given as

$$E_{dissipated / cycle} = \int A_{cycle} \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

And the total energy dissipated for the entire test is

$$E_{dissipated total} = \sum_1^n E_{dissipated / cycle} \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

where n is the total number of cycles.

During an earthquake, without undue damage a structure must be able to temporarily store part of the input energy as strain energy, and then dissipate the energy by inelastic deformation in the members. The energy dissipated in this way is equal to the area enclosed by the hysteresis loops. Shown in Figure 9-2 is a member with perfectly elasto-plastic response. The energy dissipated during a complete displacement cycle is the shaded area of the parallelogram $BCDE$. For a particular displacement level, μ , the ideal plastic energy dissipated, E_p , is given as

$$E_p = 4(\mu - 1)V\Delta_y \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

where μ is the displacement ductility factor, V is the maximum shear force attained at that given displacement factor, and Δ_y is the prescribed yield displacement

Figure 2 Theoretical Hysteretic Energy Dissipation Model (11)

One major application for DHFRP bars subjected to reverse cyclic loading is bridge piers. Under seismic loading, the pier behaves as a beam-column and is subjected to both axial loads and bending moments. The interaction between these combined loadings must therefore be studied. The basic interaction equation is given as

$$\frac{P}{P_{\max}} + \frac{M}{M_{\max}} = 1 \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

The interaction diagram for the model DHFRP R/C column reinforced with four 5-mm diameter bars and a companion steel R/C column is shown in Figure 3. At a certain axial load level ($P = 5 \text{ kN}$ for DHFRP and $P = 26 \text{ kN}$ for steel), the flexural capacity of the member is maximum. For all other levels of axial load, the flexural capacity decreases. This interaction is critical in reverse cyclic loading since the energy absorption capacity is directly related to the flexural capacity of the member.

Figure 3 Axial Load- Bending Moment Interaction Diagram for 5-mm DHFRP R/C Column and Companion Model Steel R/C Column

Concrete beam-columns reinforced with DFHRP bars were tested under reverse cyclic loading. Shown in Fig. 4 is the reinforcing cage used for the columns. The bars were embedded in square concrete columns of 38.1 mm x 38.1 mm in section and 254 mm long. Four 5-mm nominal diameter DHFRP bars were placed as the longitudinal reinforcing. These were confined with hoop reinforcement called stirrups that prevented buckling of the longitudinal reinforcing and provided shear reinforcement. No. 12 steel wire was used for the stirrups.

Figure 4 DHFRP Reinforcing Cage for Reinforced Concrete Columns

The column was loaded at its tip and was cycled through both tensile and compressive loads. Both tip deflection and base rotation were measured. The test setup is shown in Figure 5. A loading device was designed to exert both axial and lateral loads through a loading cap mounted to the top of the column. Articulations were provided to prevent any restrained motion in both translational and rotational degrees-of-freedom. Four LVDTs (Linear Variable Differential Transducers) were used to measure rotation and curvature at the base of the column and one was used at the tip to measure lateral displacement. Two load cells were used; one to measure axial load and one to measure reversed lateral loads. Figure 6 shows the loading sequence used. The load was applied based on the definition of the displacement ductility factor which is

$$\mu = \frac{\Delta_{actual}}{\Delta_{yield}} \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

Once the yield displacement was determined, the specimen was loaded in two complete cycles at each level of the displacement ductility factor.

Figure 5 Cyclic Loading Test Setup

Figure 6 Loading Sequence for R/C Column Tests

Shown in Fig. 7 is the model beam-column during testing. Fig. 8 shows the location of a plastic hinge at the base of the column where the stresses are maximum. By the formation of this plastic hinge, the inelastic material behavior of DHFRP is demonstrated. Shown in Fig. 9 is the result of a reverse cyclic load test. As seen in the load cycles, the energy absorption capacity of the DHFRP material is significant. The hysteresis loops illustrate two key points. First, the DHFRP bars show energy absorption capability,

unique when compared with most composite materials. Second, the ductility of the DHFRP is further quantified by this energy absorption capacity. This is particularly valuable in design and retrofit of reinforced concrete structures in regions of high seismicity. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 7 Reverse Cyclic Concrete Column Test Reinforced with DHFRP Bars

Figure 8 Formation of Plastic Hinge at Location of Maximum Stress

Figure 9 Load-Extension Results Of Cyclic Loading Test On 10-mm DHFRP Bars

Table 1 Summary of Cyclic Tests

Specimen	Max Load (kN)	Max Deflection (mm)	Min. Load (kN)	Min. Deflect. (mm)	Max. Moment (kN-mm)	Max. Rotation (mm ⁻¹)	Min. Moment (kN-mm)	Min. Rotation (mm ⁻¹)
C1	1.21	11.94	-1.08	-11.94	211.95	0.017	-192.97	-0.015
C2	0.81	13.21	-0.85	-10.92	140.66	0.010	-157.61	-0.005
C3	0.67	16.51	-1.15	-16.256	134.22	0.020	-240.53	-0.013

CONCLUSIONS

The Ductile Hybrid Fiber Reinforced Polymer (DHFRP) bar shows much promise in the design of new reinforced concrete structures and retrofitting existing structures, especially in areas of moderate to high seismicity. Beam-column R/C specimens subjected to reverse cyclic loading were tested to failure. From these tests, the energy absorption capacity of the DHFRP bars is significant, with a large amount of hysteresis. Also, the ductility of DHFRP was verified with the formation of a plastic hinge at the base of the model beam-column. The DHFRP bar could be used in the design of R/C structures in regions of moderate to high seismicity.

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